

WORD FINAL <f> AND <h>
(DIE KONSONANTENSCHWÄCHUNG)

This paper argues that Notker contrasted /v≠f/ and /h≠χ/ syllable finally. This is even though he only wrote <f> and <h> word finally.¹ The essay falls into seven parts:

- 1) A brief introduction to Notker.
- 2) A contrast of Notker's six pairs of obstruent phonemes.
- 3) The standard theory--a phonological process merges Notker's word final /v≠f/ and /h≠χ/ to <v> and <h>.
- 4) The standard theory--some other mergers are graphological.
- 5) The standard theory--reasons why these other mergers are graphologically, rather than phonologically, motivated.
- 6) Those same reasons used to establish the merger to <f> and <h> as graphological.
- 7) A brief summary

¹ If the base phonological boundary is the syllable, the base graphological boundary might be the word. Words can be listed and separated in a text, syllables cannot. Apparently the graphological boundary remains, even when the word is prefixed. So [ts] in <gezíhen> 'pull, inf' is written with <Z> as in <Zíhen> 'pull, inf'; not with <ZZ> (**<gezzíhen>) as in <scázza> 'treasure, nom pl'.

1) Introduction

Notker Teutonicus lived from around 950 to 1022, much of his life in the Swiss monastery of Saint Gall. He translated several Latin manuscripts into his native Alemannic, a dialect of Old High German. His works are most famous for the "Anlautgesetz", a fortition of syllable initial obstruents.² But this is only one of the scribe's many spelling mergers, some interpreted phonologically, some graphologically. Before one can differentiate between the two types however, the phonemes themselves should be posited.

2) Obstruent Phonemes

Notker contrasts six sets of obstruents /b≠p, d≠t, k≠g, v≠f, ž≠s, h≠χ/.³ The contrast is maintained in single obstruents preceded by sonorants; both syllable initially and finally.⁴

² W. Braune and H. Eggers, *Althochdeutsche Grammatik 14. Auflage*, (Tübingen: Niemeyer, 1987), §§103.

³ In order to include /h/ into the same natural class as fricatives, the terms obstruent, fricative, and velar should technically be replaced with nonsonorant, continuant and back.

⁴ Syllable internally, obstruents can only come after other obstruents, and so are always fortis (ex: [š̥kats] <SCAZ> 'treasure, nom sg'). Syllable boundaries are provisionally placed as in Modern German. See W. Benware, *Phonetics and Phonology of Modern German*, (Washington D.C.: Georgetown Press, 1986), pp. 85-86. When the syllable boundary would land on a consonant, it is not marked. Values for vowels are

Examples can be pulled from Sehrt and Starck.⁵ The elements under discussion are underlined. For now, syllable final /v/ and /h/ are listed in three possible positions, and marked with a double asterisk.

/ʂb/	/ʂp/
[wer <u>b</u> en]	[pur <u>p</u> erən]
<uu <u>ér</u> b <u>en</u> >	<p <u>úr</u> p <u>ur</u> un>
'recruit, inf'	'purple, gen sg'

/bʂ/	/pʂ/
[war <u>b</u>]	No Example
<uu <u>ár</u> b>	
'recruit, 1st sg past'	

/ʂd/	/ʂt/
[wer <u>d</u> en]	[wor <u>t</u> o]
<uu <u>ér</u> d <u>en</u> >	<uu <u>ór</u> t <u>o</u> >
'become, inf'	'word, gen pl'

approximate, with long vowels and diphthongs ending in offglides to either [j], [w] or [ə].

⁵ E.H. Sehrt and W.H. Legner, *Notkers Wortschatz: Das gesamte Material zusammengetragen von E.H. Sehrt und T. Starck* (Halle: Niemeyer, 1955). The Zweite Lautverschiebung and Konsonantenschwächung had eliminated single /p/ and /k/ after sonorant. These two holes in the lexicon gradually fill with Latin borrowings. Whether the Latin borrowings were still recognized as such is unclear. The [k] in <fúrkun> 'trident' is not spelled with a <c>, even though this is the graph in Latin <furca>.

/d\$/	/t\$/
[w <u>ard</u>]	[w <u>ort</u>]
<uu <u>á</u> rd>	<uu <u>ó</u> rt>
'become, 3rd sg past'	'word, nom sg'

/\$/g/	/\$/k/
[bur <u>g</u> o]	[fur <u>k</u> en]
<bú <u>r</u> go>	<fú <u>r</u> kun>
'castle, gen pl'	'trident, acc sg'

/g\$/	/k\$/
[bur <u>g</u>]	No Example
<bú <u>r</u> g>	
'castle, nom sg'	

/\$/v/	/\$/f/
[wol <u>v</u> a]	[hel <u>f</u> en]
<uu <u>ó</u> l <u>u</u> a>	<hél <u>f</u> en>
'wolf, nom pl'	'help, inf'

/v\$/	/f\$/
**[wol <u>v</u>]	[hal <u>f</u>]
<uu <u>ó</u> l <u>f</u> >	<há <u>l</u> f>
'wolf, nom sg'	'help, 3rd sg past'

/v\$/	/f\$/
-------	-------

** [wɔlf]
<uuólf>
'wolf, nom sg'

/ʃž/
[muw|že]
<mûze>
'mouse, nom pl'

/žš/
[muwž]
<mûs>
'mouse, acc sg'

/ʃh/
[ruher]
<rûher>
'raw, nom masc sg str'

/hš/
** [ruəh]
<rûoh>
'raw, uninfl'

/hš/
** [ruəχ]
<rûoh>

** [wɔlf]
<uuólf>
'wolf, nom sg'

/ʃs/
[hej|sən]
<héizen>
'call, inf'

/sš/
[hiəs]
<hîez>
'call, 3rd sg past'

/ʃχ/
[buw|χe]
<bûche>
'belly, dat sg'

/χš/
[buwχ]
<bûh>
'belly, nom sg'

/χš/
** [ruəχ]
<rûoh>

'raw, uninfl'

'raw, uninfl'

3) Word Final <f> and <h> Interpreted Phonologically

No one argues that the Germanic */p/ and */k/ in <hálf> and <bûh> are fortis. The Zweite Lautverschiebung⁶ shifted them to /f/ and /χ/, realized syllable finally as [f] and [χ].

More problematical are the Germanic */f/ and */h/⁷ in <uuólf> and <rûoh>. Although the Konsonantenschwächung⁸ lenited fortis fricatives, most scholars would argue that syllable final fricatives either escaped that lenition, or reverted back to fortis fricatives before the written period. Notker wrote <f> in <uuólf> and <hálf> out of phonological reasons--both words ended in [f].

The labial and velar fricative are handled separately here. But both are often treated together, as can be gleaned from some quotes.

3.1) Labial Fricatives

Penzl and Moulton do not posit /v/ syllable finally, but only an [f] from /f/, marked as <f>.

⁶ Braune, (1987) §§83.

⁷ Some scholars will refer to this as Germanic */χ/.

⁸ Braune, (1987) §§102a.

"In final position the OHG documents show no written distinction, and it would appear that inherited /f/ had become fortis in this position: gen. *houes* /hóves/ 'court' contrasting with *sciffes* /skíffes/ 'ship', but nom. *hof* /hóf/ like *scif* /skíf/; pl. *uuolua* /wólva/ 'wolves' contrasting with inf. *helfan* /hélfan/ 'help', but sing. *uuolf* /wólf/ like pret. *half* /hálf/."⁹

"Wir können im Ahd. beobachten, daß auslautendes <f> in Morphemen zweierlei Wechsel zeigt, entweder mit inlautend <v> oder mit inlautend <ff>: z. B. *hof*, Dat. *hove*, *fimf*, *finve*, *wolf*, Gen. *wolves* und *scif*, Gen. *sciffes*, *scuof* und *giscaffan*. Eine innere Rekonstruktion aus diesem Wechsel ergäbe ein früheres auslautendes *f in Opposition zu auslautendem *ff. Die Auslautstellung erwies sich aus dem Wechsel eindeutig als entscheidend für den Zusammenfall im Vorahd., also einer der historisch belegten unmittelbar vorhergehenden Stufe."¹⁰

The schema would be:

/ʒv/

/ʒf/

[wól|va]

[hel|fən]

⁹ W. Moulton, "The Stops and Spirants of Early Germanic", *Language*, 30 (1954) p. 36.

¹⁰ H. Penzl, "Althochdeutsch /f/ und die Methoden der Lautbestimmung", *Zeitschrift für Mundartforschung*, 31:4 (1964), p. 294.

<uuól <u>va</u> >	<hél <u>fen</u> >
'wolf, nom pl'	'help, inf'
/ʒv/	/ʒf/
No Example	[h <u>alf</u>]
	<h <u>álf</u> >
	'help, 3rd sg past'
	/ʒf/
	[w <u>olf</u>]
	<uuó <u>lf</u> >
	'wolf, nom sg'

Simmler would agree. He does not posit a /v/ syllable finally in Old East Franconian. The examples he cites under /f/ include Germanic */p/ (ex: <slaf> 'sleep, nom sg') and Germanic */f/ (ex: <zuelif> 'twelve, uninfl').¹¹

The Braune Grammar does not specify a "Phonemzusammenfall". Yet its descriptions of three processes support such a merger:

1) Syllable final Germanic */f/ does not lenite:

"Die Schwächung des germ. *f* drückt sich ahd. oft durch die Graphie <u (v)> aus, vor allem im Inlaut, seltener

¹¹ F. Simmler, *Graphematisch-phonematische Studien zum althochdeutschen Konsonantismus*, (Heidelberg: Niemeyer, 1981), p. 189.

im Anlaut, aber nie im Auslaut, z.B. *faran* oder *uaran*,
auar 'wieder', *houes*, aber *hof*."¹²

2) Syllable final Germanic */p/ shifts to /ff/:

"Nach Vokalen werden die westgerm. einfachen *t, p, k* im
Ahd. zu stimmlosen Doppelspiranten *zz, ff, hh*
verschoben"¹³

3) Syllable final /ff/ reduces to /f/:

"Vereinfachung der Geminatio tritt im Ahd. stets ein:
1. im Auslaut der Wörter, z.B. *rinnan, ran; ezzan, iz;*
fel, G. felles; grif, G. griffes;"¹⁴

Wilkins is more direct:

"Im Auslaut und in der Gem. mag germ. *f*, und dies noch
zu erwähnen, völlig mit *f* (=germ. *p*) zusammengefallen
sein."¹⁵

Recently, Moulton posits only one labial fricative /f/.

Word finally, it is fortis:

"Auslautend war er kurz und fortis: kurz weil niemals

¹² Braune, (1987) §§137.

¹³ Braune, (1987) §§87.

¹⁴ Braune, (1987) §§93.

¹⁵ F. Wilkins, *Zum hochalemannischen Konsonantismus der althochdeutschen
Zeit*, (Leipzig: Fock, 1891), p. 79.

-ff- geschrieben, fortis weil niemals -u-
geschrieben."¹⁶

The schema would be:

/f\$/
[helf|fen]
<helfen>
'help, inf'

/\$f/
[wol|va]
<uuolua>
'wolf, nom pl'

/f\$/
[half]
<half>
'help, 3rd sg past'

/f\$/
[wolf]
<uuolf>
'wolf, nom sg'

¹⁶ W. Moulton, "Zum Konsonantismus des Althochdeutschen: orthographisch, phonologisch, pädagogisch", in R. Bergmann, *Althochdeutsch*, (Heidelberg: Niemayer, 1987), p. 79.

Although this changes the analysis of fricatives, it still derives the <f> in <uuólf> from [f].

Esau proposes another variation. Instead of an /f/ in <uuólf>, he has a /v/ that undergoes fortition.

"While linguists generally agree that the fortis/lenis opposition was phonemic in both Old High German and Middle High German, particularly in the UG dialects, there were clearly some phonetic environments where that opposition was neutralized. For example, the tense labial fricative arising from the Second Sound Shift, as in *slafen* 'sleep', *helfen* 'help', etc., was always represented orthographically as *f*, never as *v*. But the lax labial fricative inherited from Germanic showed an alternation between *f* and *v* (e.g., *wolfes* or *wolves* 'gen. sg. of wolf'). In word final position, on the other hand, only the tense variant *f* occurred (e.g. *hof* 'yard' but *hoves* 'gen. sg. of yard'). A parallel situation existed among the velar fricatives."¹⁷

The schema would be:

/v/

/f/

¹⁷ H. Esau, "The Medieval German Sibilants /s/ and /z/", *Journal of English and Germanic Philology*, 75 (1976), p. 194.

[wol va]	[hel fən]
<uuól <u>lua</u> >	<hél <u>f</u> en>
'wolf, nom pl'	'help, inf'
[wolf]	[half]
<uuó <u>lf</u> >	<há <u>lf</u> >
'wolf, nom sg'	'help, 3rd sg past'

Again, although this changes the analysis of fricatives, the <f> in <uuólf> is still derived from [f].

3.2) Velar Fricatives

The standard theory for the velars parallels that of the labials. Notker writes <rûoh> and <bûh> with <h> out of phonological reasons--both words end in [χ].

Penzl and Moulton do not posit /h/ syllable finally; but only [χ] from /χ/, marked as <h>.

"Fortis velar /x/ also differed qualitatively from inherited lenis glottal /h/, as already described. The two were in contrast only between vowels. Examples *brehhan* /brêxxan/ 'break', *sehan* /zéhan/ 'see', *wihhan* /wí:xxan/ (later *wihan wíchan* /wí:xan/ 'yield', *lihan* /lí:han/ 'lend', but finally *brah*, *sah*, *weih*, *leh* /bráx, záx, wéjx, lé:x/ 'broke, saw, yielded, lent'."¹⁸

¹⁸ Moulton, (1954) p. 37.

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut (/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /x/) vorkommt."¹⁹

The schema would be:

/ʃh/	/ʃx/
[ru <u>h</u> er]	[buw <u>x</u> e]
<rú <u>h</u> er>	<bû <u>h</u> e>
'raw, nom sg masc st'	'belly, dat sg'
/hʃ/	/χʃ/
No Example	[buw <u>χ</u>]
	<bû <u>h</u> >
	'belly, nom sg'
	/χʃ/
	[ru <u>e</u> χ]
	<rû <u>h</u> oh>
	'raw, uninfl'

Simmler and Voyles would agree:

¹⁹ H. Penzl, *Lautsystem und Lautwandel in den althochdeutschen Dialekten*, (Munich: Max Hüber Verlag, 1971) p. 102.

"germ. k und germ. h in finaler postvokalischer Position in der Sprache Otfrids zu einem Phonem /x/ zusammengefallen sind".²⁰

"the change of *x* and *x''* to *h* and *h''* in North and West Germanic seems to have occurred only in initial position or before a vowel (rule A above: cf. the morphophonemic and orthographic remnant of this alternation in ModHG *hoch*, but *hohes*, *hohen* etc.)".²¹

As with the labial fricatives, the Braune Grammar does not specify a "Phonemzusammenfall". Yet its descriptions of three processes seem to support one:

1) Syllable final Germanic */h/ (analyzed as /χ/ here) does not lenite:

"Im Ahd. bleibt germ. /h/, von Ausnahmen abgesehen (vgl. §§153, 154), erhalten und wird durch das Zeichen <h> wiedergegeben. Doch ist eine Phonemspaltung eingetreten, die schon seit dem 8. Jh. erkennbar wird (Anm. 1).

Velarer Reibelaut ist h im Wort- und Silbenauslaut geblieben (z.B. *nāh*, *zōh wahsan*, *brāhta*);, ferner im Inlaut vor Konsonanten (z.B. *naht*, *fahs* 'Haar') und in der Geminatation (z.B. *bluhhen* 'brennen'; §§154 A. 7).

²⁰ Simmler, (1981) p. 98.

²¹ J. Voyles, "Gothic and Germanic", *Language*, 44 (1968), pp. 740-741.

Dagegen ist *h* im Wort- und Silbenanlaut (z.B. *hano*; *sehan*) zum Hauchlaut geworden.--Vgl. Schwarz, D. germ. Reibelaute *s, f, ch*, 1926, 62; Steinhauser, Fs Jellinek, 1928, 162."²²

2) Syllable final Germanic */k/ shifts to /χχ/

"Nach Vokalen werden die westgerm. einfachen *t, p, k* im Ahd. zu stimmlosen Doppelspiranten *zz, ff, hh* verschoben"²³

3) Syllable final /χχ/ reduces to /χ/

"Vereinfachung der Geminatio tritt im Ahd. stets ein:
1. im Auslaut der Wörter, z.B. *rinnan, ran ezzan, iz; fel, G. felles; grif, G. griffes*;"²⁴

Recently, Moulton derives [h] and [χ] from the same phoneme:

"Der Frikativ /h-x/, das heißt teils Hauchlaut, teils velarer Frikativ"²⁵

Only the fortis allophone [χ] comes syllable finally:

"Parallel zum labialen Frikativ dürfen wir wohl auch hier annehmen, daß dieses Phonem anlautend (KV-) und

²² Braune, (1987) §§151.

²³ Braune, (1987) §§87.

²⁴ Braune, (1987) §§93.

²⁵ Moulton, (1987) p. 79.

inlautend einfach (-VKV-) lenis, aber inlautend
geminiert (-VKKV-) und auslautend (-VK-) fortis war".²⁶

The schema would be:

/χ\$/
[ruher]
<ruher>
'raw, gen pl masc wk'

/χ\$χ/
[buwχ|χe]
<buche>
'belly, dat sg'

/χ\$/
[buwχ]
<buh>
'belly, nom sg'

/χ\$/
[ruəχ]
<ruəh>
'raw, uninfl'

²⁶ Moulton, (1987) p. 79.

Although this changes the analysis of fricatives, it still derives the <h> in <rûoh> from [χ].

4) Graphological Processes

Not all of Notker's mergers are interpreted phonologically.

Perhaps the most famous graphological ones would be:

- 1) Word initial <f>
- 2) Word final <g>
- 3) Word final <Z>
- 4) Umlauted vowels

4.1) Word Final <g>

Word finally, <g> can mark [k]:

"<g> ist im Ahd. 1. die gewöhnliche Entsprechung des germ.-got. *g*, und zwar regelmäßig im Fränkischen (*geban, ouga, tag*); aber auch überwiegend im Oberdeutschen...nicht selten für *k* in der Verbindung *sk*, besonders in-und auslautend (*asga, fisg*)".²⁷

"Bei N *sg* nur im Auslaut: *fisg, fleisg, disg, mennisgheit* (vgl. Piper 693). Da aber inlautend stets *sc* entspricht (*fisca, fleisco*)"²⁸

²⁷ Braune, (1987) §§177.

²⁸ Braune, (1987) §§146, Anm 4.

The pattern seems more complex. For [k], Notker writes:

<g> word finally (ex: <fís^g> 'fish, nom sg')

<q> before [w] (ex: <quán> 'win, 3rd sg past')

/ʃk/
[viš|kən]
<físken>
'fish, dat pl'

/kʃ/
[višk]
<físg>
'fish, nom sg'

In two environments, word final /g/ and /k/ merge to <g>.

4.1.1) [g] and a Borrowed [k] after Sonorant

The Konsonantenschwächung and Zweite Lautverschiebung left a hole in the lexicon for single [k] preceded by sonorant. Borrowed words gradually fill this hole, and here [g] and [k] are both marked <g>.²⁹

<k> before <i,e>, even if separated by a consonant (ex: <físken>
'fish, dat pl', <skrícchen> 'jump, inf')

<c> before other vowels, even if separated by a consonant (ex:
<físca> 'fish, acc pl', <scródôn> 'scrutinize, inf')

Few patterns hold all the time, and there are even regular exceptions for individual words. So, for example, <c> comes before <i> in <scríben> 'write, inf', perhaps under the influence of Latin <scribere>. <cc> is written in <glóccun> 'bell, gen sg', perhaps under the influence of Irish <glocc>.

²⁹ If <gh> is accepted as an allograph of <g>.

/g\$/	/k\$/
[tag]	[rok]
<tá <u>g</u> >	<ró <u>gh</u> > ³⁰
'day, nom sg'	'robe, nom sg.'

[g] and a [k] from a Reduced [kx] after Sonorant

[kχ] reduces syllable finally,³¹ allowing [k] to contrast with [g]. Both stops are written <g>.

/s <u>g</u> /	/kχ <u>s</u> /
[w <u>i</u> j <u>g</u> e]	[b <u>l</u> i <u>k</u> <u>χ</u> e]
<wí <u>g</u> e>	<blí <u>c</u> che>
'battle, dat sg'	'glance, dat sg'

/g\$/	/kχ\$/
[w <u>i</u> j <u>g</u>]	[b <u>l</u> i <u>k</u>]
<wí <u>g</u> >	<blí <u>g</u> >
'battle, nom sg'	'glance, nom sg'

4.2) Word Initial <f>

³⁰ This is a very poor example. <rógh> occurs twice with the stop word finally in Alemannic, and twice with the stop word medially in Latin (ex: <roccis>, <rokkos>). The word is of Germanic origin, and ends in [k]. But how Notker understood it (i.e. with an Alemannic root of */rokχ/ or a Latin root of */rok/) is difficult to say. One wishes for an inflected Alemannic form (ex: *<rócches> or *<róckes>) to determine what phoneme <rógh> has syllable finally.

³¹ Braune, (1987) §144, Anm 4.

In addition to marking [f] (and even often [v])³², <f> is:

"regelmässiger Vertreter der sonstigen ahd. *ph*, *pf* (im Anlaut und nach Konsonanten *flegen*, *chamf*);"³³

The Konsonantenschwächung and Zweite Lautverschiebung left a hole in the lexicon for word initial /f/.³⁴ But syllable initial /v/ becomes fortis when not preceded by a sonorant, allowing [f] and [pf] to contrast. Yet both are written <f>.

/R\$V/ ³⁵	/R\$pf/
[ə <u>r</u> vareŋ]	[gə <u>pf</u> legēŋ]
<eru <u>á</u> ren>	<ge <u>fl</u> égen>
'go, inf'	'care, inf'
/T\$V/	/T\$pf/
[u <u>wf</u> faren do]	[das <u>pf</u> legēŋ]
<ú <u>ff</u> árendo>	<daz <u>fl</u> égen>
'go, uninfl past part'	'care, inf'

4.3) Word Final <z>

Word finally, [s] and [ts] merge to <Z>.

³² Braune, (1987) §§103, Anm 3.

³³ Braune, (1987) §§176.

³⁴ This hole is gradually filled with foreign words. Perhaps <fúrkun> 'trident', from Latin <fúrcā>, would be an example.

³⁵ /R/ denotes any sonorant, /T/ any obstruent.

"Ahd *z* hat die Geltung einer Affrikata und entspricht...der germ. und westgerm. Germinata *tt* stets im Auslaut (*scaz*)."³⁶

"Ahd. *z* hat die Geltung eines Spiranten...und entspricht dem germ. *t* nach Vokal stets im Auslaut (*saz, uz*)."³⁷

/ʒs/	/ʒts/
[hej sən]	[škat sa]
<h <i>é</i> izen'	<scá <i>z</i> za>
'call, inf'	'treasure, nom pl'

/sʒ/	/tsʒ/
[hiəs]	[škats]
<h <i>é</i> ez>	<scá <i>z</i> >
'call, 3rd sg past'	'treasure, nom sg'

4.4) Umlauted Vowels

Some umlauted vowels are distinguished from their unfronted counterparts:

/yj/	/uw/
[hyj žer]	[huwž]
<h <i>í</i> user>	<h <i>û</i> s>
'house, nom pl'	'house, nom sg'

³⁶ Braune, (1987) §191.

³⁷ Braune, (1987) §191.

Others are not.³⁸

/øø/	/oø/
[š̥køø nij]	[š̥koø no]
<scôni>	<scôno>
'beauty, nom sg'	'beautifully, adv'

5) Reasons Interpreted Graphologically

Scholars have cited several reasons to establish these four mergers as graphologically, rather than phonologically, motivated. One might break them down into appeals to:

- 1) Related Dialects
- 2) Spelling Patterns in other Environments
- 3) Spelling Patterns in the Source System
- 4) Simpler Historical Processes

5.1) Related Dialects

For the mergers to <f> and <z>, Penzl writes:

"Bei Notker finden wir im Anlaut außer dem *f*, das mit *u* wechselt, auch ein *f*, dem in anderen Denkmälern die Schreibung *ph* oder *pf* entspricht, und für welches der Lautwert einer labialen Affrikata angenommen wird: *fálenzcráven* 'Pfalzgraf' (Akk.), *flégen* 'pflegen

³⁸ There are sporadic markings of /ø/ and other umlaut vowels. See Penzl, (1971) pp. 99-100.

(praesidere)', *fáfen* 'sacerdotes', aber *sképfo*
'Schöpfer'.³⁹

"Für den Auslaut gilt das gleiche für Z, das sowohl
Affrikata wie auch Spirans bedeuten kann: *scúz* 'Schuß',
scáz 'Geld, Schatz'.⁴⁰

Both of these rules are established by referencing contrasts
found in related dialects--whether in "anderen Denkmälern"
or Penzl's Modern German.

5.2) Spelling Patterns in other Environments

For the merger to <f>, Penzl writes:

"Notkers Wechsel zwischen den Zeichen *u* und *f* (*uáren*,
fáren) deutet auf diese Anlautsallophone hin, wobei wie
bei den Verschlusslauten zumindest eine >>Halbfortis<< *f*
im engen Anschluß an vorhergehende Geräuschlaute
wahrscheinlich ist: z.B. in *ûzfárendo* >herausfahrend<;
nâhfárendo.⁴¹

"Nichtwechselndes *f* des Anlauts (*fáfen*, *flégen*), dem im
In- und Auslaut *pf* gegenübersteht, entspricht im
Alemannischen z.T. prägraphischem *f*, aber

³⁹ H. Penzl, "Zur Erklärung von Notkers Anlautgesetz", *Zeitschrift für
deutsches Altertum*, 86 (1955), p. 205.

⁴⁰ Penzl, (1955) p. 205.

⁴¹ Penzl, (1971) p. 102.

postgraphischem *pf*, *ph* (Psalter: *phád*). Das begünstigt eine Interpretation als Affrikata /pf/ trotz aller Zeichenüberschneidung mit dem Reibelaut *f* (*fáren*), denn die Postgraphien können nicht als Ausdruck eines Lautwandels *f*>*pf* gedeutet werden. Die Überschneidung ist parallel zu der des Zeichens *z* (*dáz*, *scáz*). Es besteht deswegen auch kein Grund zu einer Interpretation als Einzelphonem statt Phonemverbindung."⁴²

"Nichtwechselndes *f*" is juxtaposed against an <*f*> that shows "Wechsel zwischen den Zeichen *u* und *f*". Although /*v*/ and /*pf*/ are both written <*f*> in fortis environments, they split into <*u*> and <*f*> in lenis ones. This spelling pattern in the lenis environment, allows one to see through the graphological merger in the fortis environment.

A second, perhaps weaker, appeal to related spelling patterns, is Penzl's reference to the dentals--"Die Überschneidung ist parallel zu der des Zeichens *z* (*dáz*, *scáz*)". Notker has three rows of continuant obstruents, /*v*,*f*,*pf*; *ž*,*s*,*ts*; *h*,*χ*,*kχ*/. But he only has two rows of graphs for them, <*v*,*f*; *s*,*z*; *h*,*ch*>.⁴³ In the

⁴² Penzl, (1971) p. 103.

⁴³ An third row of purely affricate graphs (<*pf*,*zz*,*cch*>, ex: <*sképfen*> 'create, inf', <*scázza*> 'treasure, nom pl', <*blícche*> 'glance, dat sg') are apparently not allowed at some word boundaries.

dentals, one graph <z> can mark both the affricate and fortis fricative (ex: <dáz> [das], <scáz> [škats]). This pattern in the dentals allows one to posit an identical pattern in the labials. One graph <f> can mark both the affricate and fortis fricative (ex: <fáren> [farẽn], <fáfēn> [pfafēn]).

5.3) Latin Spelling Patterns

The source writing system for Notker was Medieval Latin, or perhaps some other system originally based on Latin. Its influence on Notker's Alemannic system could be broken down into:

- 1) Latin Phonemes
- 2) Latin Phoneme Patterns

5.3.1) Latin Phonemes

Fitting Alemannic phonemes into a Romance alphabet could not have been easy. Clausen writes:

"the primary reason for Notker's failure to indicate affricates or rounded front vowels was the lack of suitable orthographic symbols at his disposal."⁴⁴

For example, Latin did not contrast /ø≠o/, but only had an <o> for [o] (ex: <fauores>). It would be natural for Notker to write both [ø] and [o] as <o>.

⁴⁴ S. Clausen, "Notker's Anlautgesetz", *Journal of English and Germanic Philology*, 78 (1979), p. 367.

/øe/	/oe/
{š <u>k</u> øe ni}j]	[š <u>k</u> oe no]
<sc <u>ô</u> ni>	<sc <u>ô</u> no>
'beauty, nom sg'	'beauty, adv'

Note that in graphology, just as in phonology, a natural process is not a required process. The lack of front rounded vowels in Latin made it natural for Notker to mark fronted and unfronted ones with the same graphs. But it was not required:

/yj/	/uw/
[hyj žer]	[huwž]
<h <u>í</u> user>	<h <u>û</u> s>
'house, nom pl'	'house, nom sg'

5.3.2) Phoneme Sequences not in Latin

One could take Clausen's argument a step further. Latin phoneme sequences, in addition to just single phonemes, could influence Notker's script. That is, it would be natural for Notker to write two phoneme sequences with the same graphs, if the sequences did not contrast in Latin. This would be so, even if Latin contrasted those phonemes in other environments.

For example, Latin contrasted [g≠k] in <gloria> and <clara>. But it did not contrast [g#] with [k#]. Only one velar stop

came word finally (ex: <hic>).⁴⁵ Given this, it would be natural, though not required, for Notker to not contrast the two velar stops word finally:

/ʒg/	/kʒχ/
[wi <u>j</u> ge]	[bli <u>k</u> χe]
<wi <u>g</u> e>	<bli <u>c</u> che>
'battle, dat sg'	'glance, dat sg'
/gʒ/	/kχʒ/
[wi <u>j</u> g]	[bli <u>k</u>]
<wi <u>g</u> >	<bli <u>g</u> >
'battle, nom sg'	'glance, nom sg'

5.4) Simplifying Historical Processes

Notker only regularly marks umlaut of /a/ and /uɯ/:

/yj/	/uɯ/
[hy <u>j</u> žər]	[hu <u>ɯ</u> ž]
<hi <u>u</u> ser>	<h <u>u</u> s>
'house, nom pl'	'house, nom sg'
/æ/	/a/

⁴⁵ /k/ is palatizing in Medieval Latin (ex: Modern German <Kreuz> from Medieval Latin <crucem>). It is difficult to say what Notker did with Latin /k/ syllable finally--whether he pronounced Latin <hic, haec, hoc> with [k] or [ts]. But this uncertainty over even one Latin velar stop syllable finally, only makes it less likely for Notker to write two word finally in Alemannic.

[væ̃rət]	[vārən]
<férit>	<fāren>
'go, 3rd sg pres'	'go, inf'

/a/ and /u̯/ are about as dissimilar as any two vowels can be. An umlaut affecting only them is a challenging rule to write. Voyles attempts it⁴⁶, positing a structural description (i.e. the phonemes undergoing umlaut) as:

OPT--/a/ [+vowel]
 [+back]
 [+low]
 [-long]
 [+stressed]

OPT--/u̯/ [+vowel]
 [+back]
 [+high]
 [+long]
 [+stressed]

The standard theory of umlaut is much simpler. King⁴⁷, in a generative reformulation of Twaddell⁴⁸, can write:

⁴⁶ J. Voyles, "A History of OHG I-Umlaut", *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache*, 113 (1991), p. 179. Voyles also writes descriptions for /õ/ and /æ̃/, but has them umlauting "rarely at all".

⁴⁷ R. King, *Historical Linguistics and Generative Grammar*, (New Jersey: Englewood Cliffs, 1969), p. 94.

[+vowel]

For most scholars, this simpler historical process justifies graphological mergers where umlaut is not marked. Penzl, for example, argues:

"Erwägungen der Struktur des Lautsystems und die Annahme von Reihenschritten bei der Phonemspaltung, d.h. von paralleler Entwicklung paralleler Phonemeinheiten zwingen uns, Schreibungsbeweise für ein oder zwei Umlautsphoneme als Beweis für das Vorhandensein sämtlicher einschlägiger Umlautsphoneme anzunehmen."⁴⁹

6) Merger to <f> and <h> Conditioned Graphologically

The appeals cited in the previous section can be used to establish a graphological merger to <f> and <h>:

- 1) Related Dialects
- 2) Spelling Patterns in Other Environments
- 3) Spelling Patterns in the Source System
- 4) Simpler Historical Processes

6.1) Related Dialects

⁴⁸ W. Twaddell, "A note on Old High German umlaut", *Monatshefte*, 30 (1938), pp. 177-181.

⁴⁹ Penzl, (1971) p. 117.

If [f] and [v] contrasted syllable finally in the ancestors of Modern German, a syllable final fortition ended this in the middle period.⁵⁰ Modern German <Wolff> and <halff> both end in [f], as <Wortt> and <wardt> both end in [t].

But some Alemannic areas⁵¹ escaped this fortition. Strangely, they do not reflect the standard theory of the language before the middle period. Syllable final Germanic */f/ and */p/ have not merged:

"Southern Swiss dialects seem to show a distribution of fortis and lenis that is even more archaic than that of the OHG documents. They have the fortis-lenis contrast not only medially (offə 'open' vs. ofə 'oven'), but also finally, even after long vowel (šlɔ:ff 'sleep' vs. gro:f 'count') and after consonant (dɔ:rff 'village' vs. wolf 'wolf')." ⁵²

Middle High German Syllable Final Fortition affected all obstruents--it would have been enough to merge the

⁵⁰ H. Paul, P. Wiehl and S. Grosse, *Mittelhochdeutsche Grammatik*, 23. Auflage, (Tübingen: Niemayer 1989), §§62.

⁵¹ How near these dialects are to Notker's Alemannic is beyond the scope of this paper.

⁵² Moulton, (1954) p. 36. Although Moulton's notation (šlɔ:ff, gro:f) reminds one of single versus geminate consonants, his terms are unambiguous--"fortis-lenis contrast". That the fricatives contrast is perhaps more important than what the contrast is called.

fricatives. To account for the data, Moulton need only have made the distribution more archaic than that.

But to fit the data into the standard theory, he has to push the dialect back before an even earlier fortition⁵³ of just fricatives, back to "a distribution of fortis and lenis that is even more archaic than that of the OHG documents". The history of the dialect is made more complex, it must miss two fortitions instead of one.

6.2) Related Spelling Patterns

Perhaps two patterns could be used to argue for a /v≠f/ and /h≠χ/ contrast syllable finally:

- 1) Nasals before <f>
- 2) Long, high vowels before <h>

6.2.1) Nasal Assimilation before <f>

⁵³ Or lack of lenition. It varies between scholars whether the Konsonantenschwächung failed to lenite fricatives syllable finally, or did lenite them, but they soon after reverted to fortis. The former is the view of the Braune Grammar. The latter view allows Penzl and Moulton to posit processes conditioned by lenis fricatives (ex: lowering by /h/) in between the Konsonantenschwächung and Old High German documents. This paper treats both scenarios as just different versions of the standard theory.

Nasals assimilate in place to a following obstruent, so should not contrast before any.⁵⁴ But although Germanic */f/ and */p/ are both spelled <f> word finally, they condition a pattern in a preceding nasal.

"Während *m* vor ahd. *ph*, *ph*, *f* (=germ. *p*, §§131) in der Regel bleibt (z.B. *kempfo*, *kemfo*, nur ausnahmsweise *kenfo* T), zeigt das *m* vor germ. *f* im Ahd. die Neigung in *n* überzugehen."⁵⁵

/ (n,m) v /	/ (n,m) (f,pf) /
[vym ve]	[glim pflīx̥eə ro]
<fínue>	<gelímflichêro>
'five, fem pl'	'suited, fem dat sg'
[vymf]	[glampf]
<fínf>	<gelámf>
'five'	'suit, 3rd sg past'

This is used to argue two things:

- 1) That a [p] is inserted (whether through the Zweite Lautverschiebung or epenthesis) between the /f/ from Germanic */p/, and a preceding homorganic nasal.⁵⁶

⁵⁴ At least morpheme internally, as in the examples here, if not everywhere. See Braune, (1987) §§123, §§125.

⁵⁵ Braune, (1987) §§123 Anm 1.

⁵⁶ Braune, (1987) §§87.

2) That "das früher bilabiale germ. f in Ahd.
labiodental geworden war"⁵⁷

The second point should be discounted. It forces Notker to mark something less noticeable than phonemes and their mergers.⁵⁸

The first point prevents one from using the nasals to posit [v≠f] syllable finally. <nf#≠mf#> could mark an [mv\$≠mpf\$] contrast, and establish [v] syllable finally.

/mv\$/ [vymv] <fínf> 'five'	/mpf\$/ [glampf] <gelámf> 'suit, 3rd sg past'
--------------------------------------	--

But it could also just mark [mf\$=mpf\$], and not establish [v].

/mf\$/ [vymf] <fínf> 'five'	/mpf\$/ [glampf] <gelámf> 'suit, 3rd sg past'
--------------------------------------	--

⁵⁷ Braune, (1987) §§123, Anm 1.

⁵⁸ The issue is addressed implicitly by any phonological analysis based on texts. But for works dealing explicitly with the controversy, see citations in King (1969), pp. 203-213; Voyles, (1991) pp. 161-164.

Both scenarios contrast phonemes, and so are eligible to be marked.⁵⁹

6.2.2) Long, High Vowels before <h>

Although Germanic */h/ and */k/ are both written <h> word finally, they condition a pattern in a preceding long, high vowel. Germanic /k/ left the vowels alone, while Germanic */h/:

"hat infolge seiner tief gutturalen Aussprache bei N
das *î* zu *îe*, das *û* zu *ûo* diphthongiert"⁶⁰

/ʃh/	/ʃx/
[ru <u>h</u> er]	[buw <u>x</u> e]
<ru <u>h</u> er>	<bû <u>h</u> e>
'raw, nom masc sg str'	'belly, dat sg'
/hʃ/	/χʃ/
[ru <u>h</u>]	[buw <u>χ</u>]
<ru <u>h</u> >	<bû <u>h</u> >
'raw, uninfl'	'belly, nom sg'

⁵⁹ The latter case however might restrict epenthesis from fricatives. Otherwise /mf/ in /vimf/ and /glampf/ both merge to [mpf], leaving no contrast to be marked by <fînf> and <gelámf>. The Braune Grammar posits epenthesis between nasals and fortis stops. One would like to maximize the rule to all fortis obstruents.

⁶⁰ Braune (1987), §§158, Anm 8. This section also goes into why <ruher> is not spelled with a long vowel, as in **<ruher>.

One could explain the pattern by positing a rule:

- 1) Syllable final Germanic */h/ lowers the offglide in long, high vowels.

But the standard theory is more complex:

- 1) Syllable final Germanic */h/ lowers the offglide in long, high vowels.
- 2) Germanic */h/ merges with Germanic */k/, to Alemannic /χ/. With the conditioning factor gone, the vowels remain diphthonged.

Proponents of the standard theory are up front about this complexity. Penzl, for example, writes:

"Es findet sich bei Notker *ûo îe* vor germ. *h statt ahd. *î û: rûoh* 'rauh', *lîehti* 'levitas, Leichtigkeit', aber *bûh* 'Bauch', *gelîh* 'gleich' mit ahd. *h* aus germ. *k...Diese vokalische Verteilung weist auf ein Stadium zurück, wo germ. *h* und ahd. *h* (aus germ. *k) im Auslaut noch nicht zusammengefallen waren."⁶¹

"Hier spiegelt sich im Auslaut eine Periode wieder, wo *h und *x (aus germ. *k) noch nicht zusammengefallen waren."⁶²

⁶¹ Penzl, (1968) p. 139.

⁶² Penzl, (1972) p. 103. See also previous citations by Moulton and A. Lloyd, "Vowel plus h in Notker's Alemannic", *Germanic Studies in Honor*

Venneman however, argues for the simpler process. He writes about a different lowering (Old High German instead of Alemannic). But the analysis of the laryngeal can be transferred to Notker:

"I turn now to *h* which like *r*, lowers the gliding vowel of *ai au* in OHG. What was the phonetic nature of this *h*? Two factors are important in the identification of this sound. The first is that only the *h* deriving from Gmc. *h* (PIE *k*) has this effect; before *h* (*hh, ch*) deriving from Gmc. *k* by the High German consonant shift, the diphthongs remain, e.g. *eih* (cf. *oak*), *zeihhan* (cf. *token*), *rouh* (cf. *reek*) *bouhhan* (cf. *beacon*). The latter was a velar fricative, as we know from the combined evidence of its origin (from [k]) and its present-day reflexes ([x] and [ç]). The lowering *h* was, therefore, not [x]."⁶³

In a later essay, Vennemann even calls for a graphological merger. In an article on the age of the second soundshift, he refutes an argument based on the Old High German monophthongization before Germanic */h/.

of Edward Henry Sehrt, Miami Linguistic Series No 1, (Coral Gables, Florida: University of Miami Press, 1968) p. 110.

⁶³ T. Vennemann, "Phonetic Detail in Assimilation: Problems in Germanic Phonology", *Language*, 48:4 (1972), pp. 874-875.

"Dieser Versuch scheitert daran, daß man nur zwei verschiedene, beide durch <h> bezeichnete Frikative anzunehmen braucht, deren verschiedenes Alter sich in verschiedenen Positionen auf der universellen Entwicklungsskala x>χ>h>Null, manifestiert. Ich selbst nehme eine Opposition von x ("germanisch h") und x ("althochdeutsch h") an, indem auf diese Weise zugleich erklärlich wird, warum es überhaupt zur Monophthongierung in den bekannten Umgebungen kommt".⁶⁴

6.3) Latin Spelling Patterns

Neither labial or velar fricatives contrasted syllable finally in Latin.

6.3.1) Labial

Although /f/ and /v/ contrast in at least Medieval Latin⁶⁵, neither occurs word finally. Given this, it would be natural (though not required) for Notker to not contrast /v≠f/ word finally.

⁶⁴ T. Vennemann, "Betrachtung zum Alter der hochgermanischen Lautverschiebung", in R. Bergmann, *Althochdeutsch*, (Heidelberg: Niemeyer, 1987), p. 46.

⁶⁵ The earlier contrast was between /f/ and /w/, evidenced by Latin borrowings into German. Contrast Notker's <uuîn> 'wine, nom sg.' from Latin <uinum> with <uêrs> 'verse, nom sg.' from Latin <uersus>. See Braune, (1987) §§137, Anm 2.

Indeed, word finally, <u> marks a vowel in Latin and in Notker (ex: <dû> 'Alemannic, you sg nom', <tu> 'Latin, you sg nom'). Can one really require the scribe to also use <u> here to write a [v] in **<uuólu> [wolv] 'wolf, nom sg'?⁶⁶

6.3.2) Velar

[h] only occurred syllable initially in Latin (ex: <honor>) and one wonders if it was still even there in the Medieval Latin of Notker's day. [χ] did not exist. <ch> and <h> both occur in Latin (ex: <pulchrem>, <Christus>, <honor>), but neither comes word finally. Given this, it would be natural (though not required) for Notker to not contrast /h≠χ/ word finally.

6.4) Simplifying Historical Processes

No one argues that Old High German obstruents could be lenis in clusters. But before the middle period, "syllable final" is not a fortis environment. /t/ and /d/ contrast in:

⁶⁶ As in the example, any word final <u> in Notker always represents a stressed vowel, and is marked with a diacritic. Unstressed [i,e,a,o,u] reduce to three vowels in open syllables, marked (without diacritics) with <e,a,o>. The argument against using <u> in **<uuólu> [wolv] 'wolf, nom sg' would be stronger if applied to an earlier Old High German text, say Isidor. Here there are no diacritics over vowels, and <u> for [u] is written word finally (ex: <uwillu> [wil|lu] 'want, 1st sg pres indic'). What influence other Old High German documents had on Notker's source system is beyond the scope of this paper.

/d\$/	/t\$/
[w <u>ard</u>]	[w <u>ort</u>]
<uu <u>á</u> rd>	<uu <u>ó</u> rt>
'become, 3rd sg past'	'word, nom sg'

6.4.1) Simpler Konsonantenschwächung

A Konsonantenschwächung that excludes syllable final fricatives would be more complex than one that does not. For clarity, the standard theory is broken down into two rules here, but they could easily be combined into one.

1) Lenition of Fricatives:

[-son]
 [+cont] -> [-fortis]

2) Fortition of Syllable Final Fricatives:

[-son]
 [+cont] -> [+fortis] / ___\$

An alternative theory need only posit lenition:

1) Lenition of Fricatives:

[-son]
 [+cont] -> [-fortis]

6.4.2) Possible Side Effects

A simpler process is only disguised as such, if it causes complexities elsewhere. The next two paragraphs examine

what effect a revised Konsonantenschwächung would have on:

- 1) Other phonemes besides /f/ and /h/
- 2) The history of German

6.4.2.2) Effect on Other Phonemes

More than just Germanic */f/ and */h/ underwent the Konsonantenschwächung. The Braune Grammar speaks of:

"eine Lenierung der stimmlosen Spiranten /f, þ, s, x/"⁶⁷

An alternative Konsonantenschwächung would lenite syllable final Germanic */š/ and */þ/ to /ž/ and /ǫ/. But it would not affect the distribution of phonemes. The standard theory does not merge a syllable final */š/ or */þ/ with the new /s/ from shifted Germanic */t/.

Germanic: */š/	*/þ/	*/t/
Notker: /š/	/þ/	/s/
[waš]	[warþ] ⁶⁸	[was]
<wás>	<wárd>	<wáz>
'be, 3 sg past'	'become 3 sg past'	'what'

Neither would an alternative Konsonantenschwächung:⁶⁹

⁶⁷ Braune, (1987) §102a. If the voiced fricatives are considered allophones of voiced stops, then this can be a lenition of all fricatives.

⁶⁸ This /þ/ shifts to /d/ by Notker, but the change does not affect contrasts here. See Braune, (1987) §167.

Germanic: */š/	*/p/	*/t/
Notker: /ž/	/ð/	/s/
[waž]	[warð] ⁷⁰	[was]
<wás>	<wárd>	<wáz>
'be, 3 sg past'	'become 3 sg past'	'what'

Indeed, if one posits Notker's /h/ as something more than just a lenis /χ/⁷¹, the only fricatives to contrast in just

⁶⁹ But an alternative Konsonantenschwächung might simplify the merger of /ð/ and /p/ to /d/.

Under the standard theory, both phonemes exist in pre-Old High German. /p/ comes syllable finally, and /ð/ everywhere else. To prevent /p/ from shifting to /t/, [-fortis] must be specified in the structural change.

[-sonorant] / [-fortis]
 [-strident] -> / [-continuant]

If an alternative Konsonantenschwächung has already lenited all /p/ to /ð/, then fortition need not be specified.

[-sonorant] /
 [-strident] -> / [-continuant]

⁷⁰ This /ð/ shifts to /d/ by Notker, but the change does not affect contrasts here. See Braune, (1987) §167.

⁷¹ There is considerable support for this throughout the Germanic languages. This paper has so far mentioned two lowerings before Germanic */h/, one in Old High German and another in Alemannic. Besides some additional lowerings, there are also other types of evidence. Devoicing and spirantization are not enough to merge /h/ with /g/ in

fortition are the labials. In a sense, a simplification of the Konsonantenschwächung hinges on a [v] for the <f> in <wólf>.

6.4.2.2) Effect on History of German

In Middle High German, both theories converge. A fortition will make syllable final fricatives fortis under either scenario.

Fortition of Syllable Final Obstruents:

[-son] -> [+fortis] / ___\$

An alternative Konsonantenschwächung would not affect the evolution of labial and velar fricatives past the middle period.

7) Summary

The standard theory offers the simplest graphology. <uuólf> ends in [f], and <rûoh> in [χ], because they are spelled like <hálf> and <bûh>.

The alternative gives a more complex, though not unnatural, graphology. Word finally, <f> can mark either [v] or [f], <h> can mark either [h] or [χ]. This does not violate a contrast found in Latin.

Gothic, and fortition is not enough to merge /h/ with /χ/ in Notker's Anlautgesetz.

But this more complex graphology allows for a simpler phonology (ex: a simpler Konsonantenschwächung, a simpler lowering before /h/, a simpler history for dialects where syllable final /f/ and /v/ still contrast).

The issue goes beyond Notker's <f> and <h>, to perhaps a core problem of text reconstruction. When should a spelling merger be interpreted graphologically or phonologically? How should the two types of evidence be weighed against each other?